

KNOWLEDGE AND AWARENESS TOWARDS PHARMACOVIGILANCE AMONG PHYSICIAN WORKING IN THE CITY CENTER OF KARAMAN

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ABSTRACT Background and Objective: "Adverse Drug Reaction" (ADR) is defined as harmful and unintended effects of drugs in normal usage and dose. Pharmacovigilance (PV) deals with identification, monitoring, prevention, or minimizing the adverse effects of drugs. This study aimed to gauge the level of PV knowledge and awareness of health professionals in Karaman / Turkey. **Design, Patients and Sample Size:** The survey was concluded amongst 161 physicians located in the city of Karaman. We aimed to measure the level of awareness in the subject matter of general PV knowledge of physicians. Interviews were held face to face. **Settings:** SPSS 17,0 package program was used during statistical analyses of data. **Main Outcome Measures and Results:** 158 of 161 physicians answered the questionnaire in this study. Although 49,2% of the physicians who participated in this study mentioned that they knew the definition of PV, only 86% of this group correctly identified PV. It was determined that 11% of physicians received PV training. 80% of participants said that they had experienced adverse reactions during drug administration, but only 4% of physicians said they filled the "Adverse drug reaction form". 18% of Physicians knew that adverse drug reactions should be reported to a centre, but only one person answered the centre's name correctly. **Conclusions:** In this study showed us the knowledge of ADRs and PV are inadequate among doctors working in Karaman, so the ADR reporting among the physician was insufficient. Rigorous service training programs need to be created to eliminate this deficiency, and more in-depth information on PV must be provided in medical schools and after graduation.

KEYWORDS Pharmacovigilance, Adverse drug reactions, Survey

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO) definition, pharmacovigilance (PV) is the science and activities related to the detection, assessment, understanding and prevention of adverse drug reactions (ADRs) or any other drug-related problem. WHO defines ADR as the harmful and unwanted reaction of a drug when used in normal doses for human beings. [1] ADR is considered as the main cause of morbidity and mortality and

is a significant health policy parameter of countries. [1,2] Multiple drug usage by doctors and patients has a massive effect on ADRs. Insufficient knowledge of physicians, patients' lack of time, being misdirected by non-scientific newspaper / TV news... etc. plays a significant role in multiple drug use. This causes significant issues in pharma economy. [3]

ADRs can be seen during multiple or single drug usage and can be avoided by sufficient information and rational prescribing. Rational pharmacotherapy procedures such as; choosing an appropriate drug, identifying optimum dose, duration of use, choosing effective and secure treatment alternatives, informing the patient about diagnosis and treatment has great importance on optimizing the risk-benefit ratio of drugs. Adequate guiding on issues such as drug dosage, proper instruction about usage, warnings, effects– side effects in rational pharmacotherapy process may prevent some of the drug-related diseases. [4]

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Table 1 A: Some socio-demographics features of participants.

Year of profession	n	%
0-4 years	18	11,2
5-9 years	52	32,3
10-14 years	39	24,2
Over 15 years	49	30,4
Null	3	1,9
Total	161	100

B:

Gender	n	%
Male	119	75,3
Female	39	24,7
Total	158	100,0

In 1848's chloroform usage on pediatric patients, which caused atrial fibrillation led awareness on ADRs. Afterwards, cautiousness on drugs' possible fatal effect has increased. Administration of sulphonamide, which dissolved in ethylene glycol caused 107 patient death that led to the implementation of PV rules. [5]

One of the worst disasters which have a premonitory impact against ADR happened in 1950s. A drug name called "thalidomide" that had been using to prevent nausea during pregnancy caused phocomelia in 10.000 fetuses. This tragic accident was published in Lancet, and consequently, The Drug Safety Law was established. [6,7]

Dangerous results regarding ADR led to the organization of PV worldwide. World data on ADRs are collected at the Uppsala Monitoring Center (UMC) constituted under the auspices of the WHO's Programme for International Drug Monitoring. National PV authorities refer to UMC alerts during the decision making the process as an essential indicator. UMC continuously monitors the Vigibase for possible signals and alerts. [8] WHO points out to disease and the prescription difference between countries. These differences may vary depending on several conditions such as; genetic, dietary and socio-cultural distinctions. Also, drug production, distribution and use difference are reasons for this distinctness. All countries are advised by WHO to build their national PV system. [1]

In Turkey, PV activities started in 1985 with the establishment of the "Turkish Adverse Drug Reaction Monitoring and Evaluation Center" (TADMER) under the General Directorate of Pharmaceuticals and Pharmacy. In 1987, TADMER joined the WHO Programme as an official member. In 2005, first PV regulation, "Regulation on the Monitoring and Assessment of the Safety of Medicinal Products for Human Use" became effective. [9] With this regulation, TADMER started to conduct PV activities under the name "Turkish Pharmacovigilance Center" (TUFAM), to stress the term "Pharmacovigilance". Significant responsibilities of TUFAM are defined as: monitoring national ADR reports and drug safety alerts worldwide, communicating drug safety alerts to healthcare professionals, educating physicians and pharmacists on PV, conducting risk minimization methods

and assessing the conformity of risk management plans and periodic safety update reports. To acknowledge the activities of the national PV system, all healthcare professionals should take responsibility for PV as a sense of duty. [7] As reported in the literature, ADRs are seen at an incidence rate of 1.6-41.4% this rate decreased in less developed countries.[10]

Drug safety is one of the leading issues in medicine. [11] While PV studies accelerated in developed countries, only a few studies demonstrate deficiencies on this issue in our country. [12] These studies are pilot projects which were planned to observe understanding and awareness of physicians regarding PV and ADR in Karaman, Turkey.

MATERIAL & METHOD

In this research, physicians who are working in different branches are randomly selected. This pharmaco-epidemiological study aims to determine the knowledge and experience of physicians in a cross-sectional and descriptive structure. Data was collected via a survey by literature index.

In this study, a total of 161 physician with different specialities was interviewed face to face, and 158 of them accepted answering the survey and while three physicians rejected. There was no time limit during survey, and it took participants approximately 10 minutes to complete. Physicians weren't informed about the survey priority, and they were asked to fill out a questionnaire immediately as it was given. Thus, preliminary answers were prevented.

Table 2 The specialities of the participant doctors.

Department	n	%
Emergency unit	2	1,3
Family physician	72	45,6
Paediatric surgery	2	1,3
Paediatrics	6	3,8
Dermatology	6	3,8
Infectious diseases	2	1,3
Physiotherapy	6	3,8
General surgery	10	6,3
Chest diseases	8	5,1
Eye diseases	6	3,8
Internal medicine	8	5,1
Gynecology	8	5,1
Cardiology	8	5,1
Ear-nose-throat	2	1,3
Neurology	2	1,3
Phychiatry	2	1,3
Radiology	2	1,3
Urology	6	3,8
Total	158	100,0

Table 3 Drug groups that caused adverse effect experienced by participants.

Drug group	n	%
Antibiotics	39	39
Analgesic/Anti-inflammatory drugs	15	15
Contrast agent	8	8
Antihypertensive	8	8
Antidiabetic	6	6
Anti-spasmolytic	4	4
Iron preparations	4	4
Antipsychotic	4	4
Anticonvulsive	2	2
Anticoagulant	2	2
Fibrinolytic	2	2
Antiemetic	2	2
Anti-glaucomatous	2	2
Hypolipidemic	2	2
Total	100	100

The survey was composed of five sections which are intended to investigate: specifications (demographic factors) in first four questions, confrontation of ADR, report information of ADR, central convey of reported ADR and procedures of reported ADR.

SPSS 17,0 package program was used during statistical analyses of data. Categorical measurements [gender, duration of experience] were specified as numbers, and percentage, continuous data age, knowledge score] were summarized as average and standard deviation.

The unpaired test was performed during comparison of dual groups on continuous measurements as knowledge score, and on more than two group comparison One – way variance analysis was performed. Statistical importance level was taken as $P < .05$ in all tests.

RESULTS

3 of 161 participated physician rejected to answer survey and 119 (75,3%) of the participated physician were men, and 39 (24,7%) were women. Eighteen of participants were (11,2%) marked 0-4 years, 52 of them (32,3%) marked 5-9 years, 39 of them (24,2%) marked 10-14 years and 49 of them (30,4%) marked 15 years and more [Table 1 A, B].

Physicians with different specialities participated. 72 (45,6%) participants were family physicians and constituted a large part of the total participants [Table 2].

To the question "Do you know what PV is?" , 78 (49,4%) of participants answered "Yes" and 22 (13,9%) answered "No". 67 (93,0%) of a participant who answered "yes" to this question, defined PV correctly and rest of 11 (14,0%) participants defined incorrectly. To the question "Have you had any education on PV?"

Table 4 The main symptoms met as the adverse events observed by the participants.

Symptoms observed	n	%
Allergic reactions	41	41
Diarrhea	13	13
Abdominal pain	10	10
Nause/vomiting	14	14
Dizziness	4	4
Cough	4	4
Anaphlaxis	2	2
Leg swelling	2	2
Balanitis	2	2
Extrapyramidal system side effects	2	2
Galactorrhea	2	2
Myalgia	2	2
Syncope	2	2
Total	100	100

" 18 (11,4%) of the participants answered "Yes", and 140 (88,6%) of participant answered "No." Among those who have answered "yes", 8 (44,4%) of them marked source of education as " in-service educational programs", 3 (16,7%) of them marked "by pharmacology books", 3 (16,7%) of them marked "via internet" and rest of 4 (22,2%) participant marked as "in pharmacology class in medical faculty".

To the question "Have you ever experienced any adverse effects of the drug you have administered to the patient?" 127 (80,4%) of the participant answered "yes" 31 (19,6%) participant answered "No".

127 physician was asked if the patient complained of adverse effect after drug prescription, 31 (19,6%) of them left question unanswered [Table 3]. Participants who observed the adverse effect on drugs administered were asked about symptoms. Allergic reactions were a common answer. Other symptoms presented in Table 4.

To the question "Are you aware that there is an adverse event report form?" , 124 (78,7%) of participant answered "No". To the question "Have you ever filled out an adverse event form?" , 153 (96,8%) answered "No." Participants who answered "Yes" did not answer the next question, which was "how many forms have you filled out." To the question "Do you know adverse events should be reported to a unit?" 29 (18,3%) of the participant answered "Yes", and only 1 of them answered correctly to the question of " Which unit?". To the question "Which path should you use to contact the unit that you are supposed to report the adverse event?" , 147 (93,0%) of participant did not answer the question, 7 (4,4%) participants marked the path " by e-mail", 2 of the participants (1,3%) marked "telephone" and 2 participants answered other (1,3%) "by e-mail, telephone, fax or letter". The question "Could you write down the name of the PV centre under the supervision of the Ministry of Health Drug

and Pharmaceutics Head Office" was answered correctly by 23 (14,5%) participant by marking "TUFAM".

DISCUSSION

WHO determines PV as scientific studies related to identifying, understanding and measuring adverse effects of various natural substances and sedatives. The main interest of PV is adverse side effects of medicine-medicine, medicine-food, medicine-plant relationships and also hospitalization and death related to these combinations.

Additionally, PV is also involved with measuring the risks of marketed drugs that are part of the pharma industry. Furthermore, PV aims to increase reporting of adverse reactions in a correct manner. [1]

ADR is defined as dangerous and undesired effects of drugs that are used in regular dosage. Worldwide Awareness in adverse reactions has increased rapidly after the Thalidomide disaster. Thalidomide had been used widely at the beginning of the 1950s and 60s for the treatment of nausea and vomiting experienced during pregnancy. Thousands of children had exhibited severe congenital disabilities until it was forbidden. [6] After this ADR which was also referred to as Thalidomide tragedy, worldwide working concerning the PV (drug safety) and ADR issue were created. In recent years it has been observed that there are different views regarding ADR and PV in various countries and parts of the world. For example, in the USA, there are approximately 1 million ADR related cases per year. In Germany between 8000 - 16000, deaths occur as a result of ADR in elderly patients. [2,13] This was an epidemiological pilot study concerning the difference in knowledge and attitudes of doctors working in central Karaman on PV, ADR and reporting these symptoms. Socio-demographics of our survey subjects were as follows; 119 male (75,3%) and 39 female (24,7%). Physicians who have participated in our survey came from various fields, but most were family health practitioners. In our study, we asked various questions to measure the knowledge and attitudes of physicians in regards to PV. Initially, we asked if they knew the term definition of PV. Although 49,2% of the physicians who participated in this study mentioned that they knew the definition of PV, only 93,0% of this group correctly identified PV. Hardeep and Ark held a similar survey in India with 61 participants, out of these 77,0% correctly identified PV. [14] In another study that was held in Turkey between nurses and obstetricians out of 329 participants on 23.3% identified PV correctly. [12] We think that this variance in the level of knowledge for PV amongst physicians and other health professionals from different parts of the world is caused by difference education curricula provided.

When we asked our participants "if they have ever had any education in the field of PV" we have realized that only 11.4% had any previous education in this field. Most of them who had been educated in PV stated that they received such education with on-job training, the second group stated that they received PV education at med-school and the rest received information in this field from the internet, PV textbooks and other resources. Similarly, in a study that was conducted amongst nurses and obstetricians working in the city of Adana, most participants stated that they had received education in PV while working shifts in intensive care unit, during periods of training and while receiving on-job training. [12] In a different study, we have determined that participants mostly receive this education during on-job training sessions. [15] These results show us that health-care workers do not receive sufficient education in the field of

PV while in med-school and that they graduate without enough knowledge in the field. This deficiency is then attempted, filled with on-job training.

In our study, 80.4% of participants stated that they had experienced adverse reactions during drug administration. Most commonly experienced antibiotics and analgesics caused adrs. The most common ADRs observed by the doctors participating in our study were allergic reactions (rash, redness, itching, urticaria), diarrhoea, abdominal pain, nausea/vomiting, dizziness and cough, respectively. Amongst 190 different antibiotics that are reported to TUFAM, most adverse reactions were reported accordingly; rash, diarrhoea, oedema, vomiting, itching, stomach pain, redness and allergy. [16] According to WHO, most reported ADRs are as follows; redness, itching, urticaria, fever, nausea, headache, vomiting, diarrhoea and stomach pain. [17] The most common ADRs experienced by 193 patients in the University of Harran, Turkey were urticaria (72 patients), maculopapular drug eruption (31 patients), fixed drug eruption (24 patients) and pruritus (14 patients). The most common drug groups responsible for these adverse events were antibiotics (63 patients, 32,6%), analgesics (37 patients, 19,2%) and antihypertensive drugs (19 patients, 9,8%), respectively. [18] In a study conducted in Uludağ University Dermatology Department, the most frequently encountered ADRs were urticaria and angioedema with a rate of 20.9%. Subsequently observed reactions were angioedema at a rate of 13.6% and maculopapular drug eruption at a rate of 10.2%. [19] These results show us that antibiotics and NSAIDs are the most commonly prescribed drugs in Turkey and worldwide. Regardless of the consensus, there are different adverse reactions caused by drugs in various other groups. It has been determined that doctor working in Karaman region have mostly prescribed antibiotics and analgesics to their patients. Furthermore, according to other studies done amongst doctors in various parts of the world has shown that they have similar tendencies in terms of prescription habits. When adverse reactions do not create serious consequences, these reactions are classified as low to mild. [20] Doctors are hesitant to prescribe drugs with severe adverse reactions, in our opinion.

To determine the knowledge of the participants who took place in our survey, we have asked them questions regarding Turkish Pharmacovigilance Center (TPVC). We have asked them if they knew the that TPVC is under the administration of the Turkish Ministry of Health, Turkish Drug and Medical Device Corporation. 14,0% stated that they were of this, and 85.2% stated that they were not. In a study that was done in Turkey; 59,0% of participants stated that they were aware of the national PV program. [14] This variance in different regions of Turkey has shown us that doctors working in Karaman region lack knowledge and information in regards to TPVC and national PV program due to lack of education and information. In our study, 21.3% stated that they were not aware of the need to report adverse reactions by utilising the "adverse reactions notification form" to TPVC. 78.7% stated that they were aware of the procedure, but only 53.3% stated that they fill out this form, and 46.7% stated that they did not. In a study that was conducted in South India, 88% of doctors stated they aware of the need to fill out the adverse reaction form, but only 23,0% stated that they do complete the form. [21] Adedeji and et al. conducted a study that showed that ADR reporting is at 57.1%, but International Pharmacovigilance Center determined this number to at 71.4%. [22] In another study, 71,0% of participants stated that they did

not know how to report ADRs, and the number of reported cases was as low as 5,0%. [23] In another study that was conducted in India, it has been reported that only 24.7% of doctors knew the existence of Pharmacovigilance Center and 26,0% reported ADR cases. [24] Filling out ADR forms correctly is imperative to the success of PV policies. Additionally, this causes a risk to patients and the general public.

These results show us that most doctors working in Karan region do not have enough information about TPVC. Most doctors who are aware of the TPVC do not have enough knowledge and experience to fill out adverse reaction forms. A similar finding in different parts of the world shows us that in general doctors do not have enough knowledge about where and how to ADRs. Thus far benefits of reporting ADRs is defeated by a lack of knowledge in these regions.

Doctors who have participated in our study did not state to us how to obtain adverse reactions forms. 4.4% of doctors who have answered this question stated that they would prefer e-mail. In a study that was conducted in Nigeria, it has been determined that doctors were aware of the procedure of how to report ADRs, this also shows us that doctors in various regions often lack the knowledge and information in this subject matter. It is imperative that such lack of knowledge is taken care of by providing additional education after graduating from med school. Reporting of adverse reactions by doctors during treatment has great benefits. As long as medications is prescribed, there will always be ADRs as these two go hand in hand. Adverse reactions and toxic reactions vary from patient to patient as every patient has different pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic parameters. Patients from different races also differently to ADRs. [25] Doctors must consider these variances and calculate the possible ADRs accordingly and report them to appropriate centres thus far contributing to personal and national policies. Determining education and knowledge of doctors in the field of PV will greatly aid national health policy.

Conclusion

In our study we have identified a lack of knowledge and education in determined, identifying and reporting ADRs and their results were the same all along with the study without any in a change in sex, department and experience. It is imperative that such lack of knowledge is taken care of by providing additional education after graduating from med school. Further improvements in this field will increase life quality and reduce the amount of time and money spent on health service.

Competing Interests

None

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